

Lepton Flavour Universality tests and determination of $|V_{us}|$ using the HFLAV-Tau branching fractions fit

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Abstract

We present an update of the lepton flavour universality (LFU) tests and of the determination of the CKM matrix element $|V_{us}|$ using the latest HFLAV-Tau global fit of τ branching fractions. The fit accounts for all correlations and dependencies on common external inputs.

1 HFLAV fit of τ branching fractions, τ mass and τ lifetime

The HFLAV 2023 report [1] describes three fits performed on τ measurements, using the HFLAV procedures to account for the dependencies of the measurements on external inputs like other world averages, or luminosity measurements that are used for different branching fraction measurements by the same experimental collaboration.

A set of 171 measurements of τ branching fractions and ratios of branching fractions m_i and an estimate of one nuisance parameter $n_r \pm \sigma_{n_r}$ are fit to obtain 137 fit parameters q_k and 1 nuisance fit parameter p_r . The fit parameters and the nuisance fit parameter are subjected to 91 constraint equations. The minimized χ^2 is

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{ijkl} (m_i - M_{ik}q_k) (V^{-1})_{ij} (m_j - M_{jl}q_l) + \sum_r \frac{(n_r - p_r)^2}{\sigma_{n_r}^2}, \quad (1)$$

where M_{ik} is the model matrix applied to fit parameters to predict measurements and V_{ij} is the measurements' covariance. The available measurements of the τ mass and lifetime are also fit to obtain their averages.

2 Tests of lepton flavour universality

In order to test lepton flavour universality (LFU), we use the expression for the partial width of a heavier lepton \mathcal{L} decay to a lighter lepton ℓ

$$\Gamma[\mathcal{L} \rightarrow \nu_{\mathcal{L}}\ell\bar{\nu}_{\ell}(\gamma)] = \frac{G_{\mathcal{L}}G_{\ell}m_{\mathcal{L}}^5}{192\pi^3} f^{\mathcal{L}\ell} (1 + \delta R_{\gamma}^{\mathcal{L}\ell}) (1 + \delta R_W^{\mathcal{L}\ell}), \quad (2)$$

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where $f^{\mathcal{L}\ell}$ is a phase space factor that depends on the leptons' masses, $\delta R_\gamma^{\mathcal{L}\ell}$ and $\delta R_W^{\mathcal{L}\ell}$ correspond to the QED and electroweak (EW) radiative corrections, respectively [1]. We obtain:

$$\left(\frac{g_\tau}{g_\mu}\right) = \sqrt{\frac{\mathcal{B}_{\tau e} \tau_\mu m_\mu^5 f_{\mu e} R_\gamma^\mu R_W^{\mu e}}{\mathcal{B}_{\mu e} \tau_\tau m_\tau^5 f_{\tau e} R_\gamma^\tau R_W^{\tau e}}} = 1.0016 \pm 0.0014 \quad (3)$$

$$\left(\frac{g_\tau}{g_e}\right) = \sqrt{\frac{\mathcal{B}_{\tau\mu} \tau_\mu m_\mu^5 f_{\mu e} R_\gamma^\mu R_W^{\mu e}}{\mathcal{B}_{\mu e} \tau_\tau m_\tau^5 f_{\tau\mu} R_\gamma^\tau R_W^{\tau\mu}}} = 1.0018 \pm 0.0014 \quad (4)$$

$$\left(\frac{g_\mu}{g_e}\right) = \sqrt{\frac{\mathcal{B}_{\tau\mu} f_{\tau e} R^{\tau e}}{\mathcal{B}_{\tau e} f_{\tau\mu} R^{\tau\mu}}} = 1.0002 \pm 0.0011 \quad (5)$$

3 $|V_{us}|$ from τ branching fraction measurements

$|V_{us}|$ is computed using the inclusive τ branching fraction to strange hadronic final states as [2,3]

$$|V_{us}|_{\tau\text{-OPE-1}} = \sqrt{R_s / \left[\frac{R_{ud}}{|V_{ud}|^2} - \delta R_{\tau\text{-}SU(3)\text{-break}} \right]} = 0.2184 \pm 0.0021, \quad (6)$$

where $R_s = \mathcal{B}_s / \mathcal{B}_e^{\text{uni}} = 0.1632 \pm 0.0027$, $\mathcal{B}_s = 2.908 \pm 0.048$ is the inclusive τ branching fraction to strange hadronic final states, $\mathcal{B}_e^{\text{uni}}$ is the universality-improved electronic τ branching fraction [1], $R_{ud} = R_{\text{had}}^{\text{uni}} - R_s = 3.470 \pm 0.008$, $R_{\text{had}}^{\text{uni}}$ is the ratio between the inclusive hadronic τ decay branching fraction and $\mathcal{B}_e^{\text{uni}}$, $|V_{ud}| = 0.97384 \pm 0.00026$ is taken from a recent average of measurements of superallowed nuclear β decays, neutron decay measurements [4], and $\delta R_{\tau\text{-}SU(3)\text{-break}}$ accounts for the $SU(3)$ -breaking effects [5–7]. We mention also two additional $|V_{us}|$ determinations, which could not be updated because of their complexity:

$$|V_{us}|_{\tau\text{-OPE-2}} = 0.2219(22) \quad [8, 9] \quad (7)$$

$$|V_{us}|_{\tau\text{-latt-disp}} = 0.2240(18) \quad [9, 10] \quad (8)$$

An additional evaluation of $|V_{us}|$ uses the lattice QCD calculation of the inclusive τ hadronic decay rate [11],

$$|V_{us}|_{\tau\text{-latt-incl}} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{|V_{us}|^2}{R_s}\right)_{\text{latt-incl}}} \cdot R_s = 0.2189 \pm 0.0019, \quad (9)$$

where $(R_s / |V_{us}|^2)_{\text{latt-incl}} = 3.407 \pm 0.022$ [11]. All calculations of the τ inclusive decay rate to hadronic strange final states are not presently including the long-distance isospin-breaking corrections [11].

We compute $|V_{us}| / |V_{ud}|$ from the ratio of branching fractions $\mathcal{B}_{10/9} = \mathcal{B}(\tau^- \rightarrow K^- \nu_\tau) / \mathcal{B}(\tau^- \rightarrow \pi^- \nu_\tau) = 0.0644 \pm 0.0009$ using the equation [12]:

$$\frac{\mathcal{B}(\tau^- \rightarrow K^- \nu_\tau)}{\mathcal{B}(\tau^- \rightarrow \pi^- \nu_\tau)} = \frac{f_{K^\pm}^2 |V_{us}|^2 (m_\tau^2 - m_K^2)^2}{f_{\pi^\pm}^2 |V_{ud}|^2 (m_\tau^2 - m_\pi^2)^2} (1 + \delta_{\tau K/\tau\pi}), \quad (10)$$

where $\delta_{\tau K/\tau\pi} = (0.10 \pm 0.80)\%$ [13] is the radiative correction for the ratio of partial widths $\Gamma(\tau \rightarrow K \nu_\tau[\gamma]) / \Gamma(\tau \rightarrow \pi \nu_\tau[\gamma])$. Using the ratio of decay constants $f_{K^\pm} / f_{\pi^\pm} = 1.1934 \pm 0.0019$ from the 2023 web update of the FLAG 2021 lattice QCD averages with $N_f = 2+1+1$ [14–20], we obtain $|V_{us}| / |V_{ud}| = 0.2289 \pm 0.0019$. By using the above-mentioned $|V_{ud}|$ value, we compute $|V_{us}|_{\tau K/\pi} = 0.2229 \pm 0.0019$.

$|V_{us}|$ is calculated using the branching fraction $\mathcal{B}(\tau^- \rightarrow K^- \nu_\tau)$ as

$$\mathcal{B}(\tau^- \rightarrow K^- \nu_\tau) = \frac{G_F^2}{16\pi\hbar} f_{K^\pm}^2 |V_{us}|^2 \tau_\tau m_\tau^3 \left(1 - \frac{m_K^2}{m_\tau^2}\right)^2 S_{\text{EW}}^{\tau h} (1 + \delta_{\tau K}). \quad (11)$$

We use $f_{K^\pm} = 155.7 \pm 0.3$ MeV from the 2023 web update of the FLAG 2021 lattice QCD averages with $N_f = 2+1+1$ [14–16, 18, 19, 21]. The universal short-distance electroweak correction for τ hadronic decays is $S_{\text{EW}}^{\tau h} = S_{\text{EW}}^{R\tau h} \cdot S_{\text{EW}}^{\text{sub,lep}} = 1.01910 \pm 0.00030$, where the radiative correction for the τ spectral functions is $S_{\text{EW}}^{R\tau h} = 1.02350 \pm 0.00030$ [22–24] and the sub-leading universal short-distance correction for the τ leptonic decays is $S_{\text{EW}}^{\text{sub,lep}} = 0.9957$ [22]. The long-distance radiative correction for $\mathcal{B}(\tau^- \rightarrow K^- \nu_\tau)$ is $\delta_{\tau K} = (-0.15 \pm 0.57)\%$ [13]. The physical constants G_F and \hbar are taken from CODATA 2018 [25]. We obtain $|V_{us}|_{\tau K} = 0.2224 \pm 0.0017$.

We list in the following $|V_{us}|$ as predicted by the unitarity of the CKM matrix, $(|V_{us}|_{\text{uni}})^2 = 1 - |V_{ud}|^2 - |V_{ub}|^2$ (where the $|V_{ub}|$ is negligible because of its small size, $|V_{ub}| = 0.00382 \pm 0.00020$ [26]), $|V_{us}|$ evaluated with measurements of kaons' properties [4], the above $|V_{us}|$ calculations using τ measurements, the average of the τ exclusive evaluations ($|V_{us}|_{\tau K/\pi}$ & $|V_{us}|_{\tau K}$), the average of all τ evaluations, and all discrepancies with respect to $|V_{us}|_{\text{uni}}$:

$$|V_{us}|_{\text{uni}} = 0.2272 \pm 0.0011 \quad 0.0\sigma \quad [\sqrt{1 - |V_{ud}|^2 - |V_{ub}|^2} \quad (\text{CKM unitarity})], \quad (12)$$

$$|V_{us}|_{K\ell 3} = 0.2233 \pm 0.0005 \quad -3.2\sigma \quad [\mathcal{B}_{K\ell 3}], \quad (13)$$

$$|V_{us}|_{K\ell 2} = 0.2250 \pm 0.0005 \quad -1.7\sigma \quad [\mathcal{B}_{K\ell 2}], \quad (14)$$

$$|V_{us}|_{\tau\text{-OPE-1}} = 0.2184 \pm 0.0021 \quad -3.6\sigma \quad [\mathcal{B}(\tau^- \rightarrow X_s^- \nu_\tau)], \quad (15)$$

$$|V_{us}|_{\tau\text{-latt-incl}} = 0.2189 \pm 0.0019 \quad -3.7\sigma \quad [\mathcal{B}(\tau^- \rightarrow X_s^- \nu_\tau)], \quad (16)$$

$$|V_{us}|_{\tau K/\pi} = 0.2229 \pm 0.0019 \quad -2.0\sigma \quad [\mathcal{B}(\tau^- \rightarrow K^- \nu_\tau)/\mathcal{B}(\tau^- \rightarrow \pi^- \nu_\tau)], \quad (17)$$

$$|V_{us}|_{\tau K} = 0.2224 \pm 0.0017 \quad -2.3\sigma \quad [\mathcal{B}(\tau^- \rightarrow K^- \nu_\tau)], \quad (18)$$

$$|V_{us}|_{\tau \text{ excl}} = 0.2225 \pm 0.0017 \quad -2.3\sigma \quad [\text{tau exclusive average}], \quad (19)$$

$$|V_{us}|_{\tau} = 0.2208 \pm 0.0014 \quad -3.6\sigma \quad [\text{tau average}]. \quad (20)$$

All correlations arising from using the τ branching fractions fit results and common external inputs are accounted for. The systematic uncertainties of $|V_{us}|_{\tau\text{-OPE-1}}$ and $|V_{us}|_{\tau\text{-latt-incl}}$ have been assumed to be uncorrelated. The correlation between f_{K^\pm} and f_{K^\pm}/f_{π^\pm} is conservatively set to 100%. We assume that $\delta_{\tau\pi}$ and $\delta_{\tau K}$ are uncorrelated [13] and that $\delta_{\tau K/\pi} \simeq \delta_{\tau K} - \delta_{\tau\pi}$.

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